

Lost in Wikipedia: COVID-19 before the outbreak

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to identify weak signals linked to the COVID-19 disease at the end of 2019 using Wikipedia, the free online encyclopaedia in English, en.wikipedia.org.

The main step of the methodology is to use criteria to choose specific articles on drugs, diseases, viruses and scientific keywords related to COVID-19 disease and SARS-COV-2 from Wikipedia and from scientific publications. The analysis of the page views counts of these Wikipedia articles shows a weak signal for each article in the period September 2019 - December 2019. A cluster of similar signals occurs in early October 2019. The number of articles is too low to confirm the link between this cluster and concerns about the COVID-19 outbreak and further investigations are needed.

Keywords: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, Wikipedia, page views, weak signals, data mining

Introduction

Many scientific publications on COVID-19 observed searches during the years 2020 and 2021, on Google Trends or Wikipedia. For example: research about loss of taste [1], relationships between the number of searches and the number of sick people [2], predictive nature of the search volume [3], perception of the epidemic according to the country [4], most visited medical articles during the outbreak [5]. Other publications observed the construction of articles relaying scientific information on Wikipedia [6].

It is possible that people had symptoms before January 2020. On December 30, 2019, messages appeared on the social network Twitter mentioning Sars and the city of Wuhan (Fig.1). These messages relay information published on social networks in China in December 2019. Scientific publications report possible cases of COVID-19 in November 2019 and December 2019 [7], [8]. To identify if people searched for information related to the future COVID-19 disease before December 31, 2019, Wikipedia page views of selected articles are analysed.

Material and methods

The article search from Wikipedia articles on COVID-19 and SARSCOV-2 and from scientific publications needed to select specific articles. The criteria used are:

- Keyword related to the disease COVID-19 or SARS-COV-2, or to symptoms of the disease,
- Article created before 2015,
- Article rarely consulted during the period [2015-2019] from 0 to 500 views,
- Number of page views of the article showing little variation during the period [2015-2019],
- Identification of an increase in the number of page views from 500 to 1000 after September 2019 and before the end of December 2019,
- No knowledge of specific information on the keyword to the public in the media.

The analyse focuses on five groups of articles: drugs, diseases, scientific terms found in publications, viruses and articles on "human coronavirus".

The Sars keyword is difficult to analyse. A disambiguation exists between Sars "Severe acute respiratory syndrome" and Sars "Special Anti-Robbery Squad" former unit of the Nigeria Police Force. On Twitter, the Special Anti-Robbery Squad gave rise to many posts in 2019 including in December 2019. It is not possible to know if the number of consultations on the article "Severe acute respiratory syndrome" is only the result of a research on the virus. The term ageusia was not retained either. Dimitri character from Fire Emblem, role-playing video game, suffers from ageusia. This new game was released in July 2019.

The "drugs" group was constructed from the Wikipedia article "COVID-19 drug repurposing research", from the "COVID-19 drug development" article: Favipavir, Lopinavir, Ritonavir, Sarilumab, Tocilizumab, Chloroquine, and from scientific publications: Buformin [9], Ivacaftor [10], Bromhexine [11] Probucol [12].

The "diseases" articles group includes common terms, so the specificity with COVID-19 disease is low but the articles are not widely viewed. The number of the page views increased during the period.

The group of articles "scientific terms" was constructed from terms of scientific publications: nicotinic acetylcholine receptor [13], glycosaminoglycan [14], dipeptidyl peptidase 4 [15], angiotensin converting enzyme [16], protein kinase [17], pyridoxine [18], ochratoxin A [19], this keyword was chosen to test if people looked for information about neurotoxic symptoms [20].

The virus group brings together articles on coronavirus, enterovirus and articles on hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus [21], orthohepevirus A, provirus [22] this keyword was chosen to test if people looked for information about HIV, myoviridae [23] this keyword was chosen to test if people searched information about bacteriophages.

Results

At the beginning of October 2019, for each of the 31 articles in the four groups of articles (drugs diseases scientific terms and viruses) (Fig. 2, Fig. 3, Fig. 4, and Fig. 5), the number of the page views increased.

The number of consultations on "Human coronavirus" is usually low (less than 200 page views) and at the end of 2019, it was the same. Only the number of page views of the article "HKU1" increased in December 2019 (Fig. 6). The number of page views of the article "Respiratory syncytial virus" also increased in November 2019 (Fig. 7).

If we take into account the article "Severe respiratory acute syndrome", ignoring the problem of disambiguation, we observe in the period from September 2019 to December 2019 an increase in mid-October and early November (Fig. 8). At the end of December 2019, the number of consultations increased rapidly more than 3,000 page views, probably linked to the rumour of an outbreak in Wuhan.

Discussion

In this paper, the methodology is to select specific Wikipedia articles to identify, in a single period, a sudden increase of the count of page views. This methodology requires a large number of rarely consulted Wikipedia articles. The cluster of the 31 articles related to COVID-19 and SARS-COV-2 suggests that concerns close to the COVID-19 disease took place in early October 2019 before the start of the COVID-19 epidemic. The number of articles is too low to draw any conclusion about a link to the occurrence of COVID-19 cases during this period.

Figure 1. Twitter posts 30-12-2019: Sars-Wuhan, alert

Figure 2. Drugs en.wikipedia.org page views [July 2015 - December 2019] and [September 2019 - December 2019]

Figure 3. Diseases en.wikipedia.org page views [July 2015 - December 2019] and [September 2019 - December 2019]

Figure 4. Scientific keywords en.wikipedia.org page views [July 2015 - December 2019] and [September 2019 - December 2019]

Figure 5. Virus en.wikipedia.org page views [July 2015 - December 2019] and [September 2019 - December 2019]

Figure 6. Human coronavirus en.wikipedia.org page views [July 2015 - December 2019] and [September 2019 - December 2019]

Figure 7. Respiratory syncytial virus en.wikipedia.org page views [July 2015 - December 2019] and [September 2019 - December 2019]

Figure 8. Severe acute respiratory syndrome en.wikipedia.org page views [September 2019 - December 2019]. Disambiguation: the number of page views could be linked to research on “Special Anti-Robbery Squad” former unit of the Nigeria Police Force.

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